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Research Article

**SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF NEW ANALYTICAL
METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF
DICYCLOMINE AND DICLOFENAC K BY HIGH
PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY**

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Abstract:

A simple, precise, and accurate reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Dicyclomine and Diclofenac Potassium in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Phenomenex Gemini C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase of Methanol: TEA buffer (65:35 v/v), delivered at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The analysis was performed at a detection wavelength of 230 nm, using a Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC system with PDA Detector (996 model), with a column temperature of 40°C, injection volume of 10 μL, and a run time of 7 minutes. The method showed excellent linearity, accuracy, precision, and specificity, in compliance with ICH validation guidelines. The retention times of Dicyclomine and Diclofenac Potassium were well-resolved with sharp peaks and no interference from excipients. The method proved to be robust and reproducible, making it suitable for routine quality control analysis of these drugs in bulk and combined dosage forms.

Keywords: Dicyclomine, Diclofenac Potassium, RP-HPLC, Simultaneous Estimation, Analytical Method Validation, Pharmaceutical Dosage Form, Column Chromatography, Method Development.

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INTRODUCTION:

Analytic method development and validation are key elements of any pharmaceutical development program. HPLC analysis method is developed to identify, quantify or purifying compounds of interest. This technical brief will focus on development and validation activities as applied to drug products.

Method development:

Effective method development ensures that laboratory resources are optimized, while methods meet the objectives required at each stage of drug development. Method validation, required by regulatory agencies at certain stages of the drug approval process, is defined as the “process of demonstrating that analytical procedures are suitable for their intended use” [1-2]. Understanding of the physical and chemical characteristics of drug allows one to select the most appropriate high performance liquid chromatography method development from the available vast literature. Information concerning the sample, for example, molecular mass, structure and functionality, pKa values and UV spectra, solubility of compound should be compiled. The requirement of removal of insoluble impurities by filtration, centrifugation, dilution or concentration to control the concentration, extraction (liquid or solid phase), derivatization for detection etc. should be checked. For pure compound, the sample solubility should be identified whether it is organic solvent soluble or water soluble, as this helps to select the best mobile phase and column to be used in HPLC method development.

Method development in HPLC can be laborious and time consuming. Chromatographers may spend many hours trying to optimize a separation on a column to accomplish the goals. Even among reversed phase columns, there is astonishing diversity, owing to differences in both base silica and bonded phase characteristics. Many of these show unique selectivity. What is needed is a more informed decision making process for column selection that may be used before the chromatographer enters the laboratory. The method of column selection presented here involves a

minimal investment in time initially, with the potential of saving many hours in the laboratory.

Analytic methods are intended to establish the identity, purity, physical characteristics and potency of the drugs that we use. Methods are developed to support drug testing against specifications during manufacturing and quality release operations, as well as during long-term stability studies. Methods that support safety and characterization studies or evaluations of drug performance are also to be evaluated. Once a stability-indicating method is in place, the formulated drug product can then be subjected to heat and light in order to evaluate the potential degradation of the API in the presence of formulation excipients [3, 4].

The degraded drug samples obtained are subjected to preliminary chromatographic separation to study the number and types of degradation products formed under various conditions [9]. Scouting experiments are run and then conditions are chosen for further optimization [10]. Resolving power, specificity, and speed are key chromatographic method attributes to keep in mind during method development [11]. Selectivity can be manipulated by combination of different factors like solvent composition, type of stationary phase, mobile phase, buffers and pH. Changing solvents and stationary phases are the most comfortable approaches to achieve the separation. The proper range of pH is an important tool for separation of ionizable compounds. Acidic compounds are retained at low pH while basic compounds are more retained at higher pH. The neutral compounds remain unaffected. The pH range 4-8 is not generally employed because slight change in pH in this range would result in a dramatic shift in retention time. However, by operating at pH extremes (2-4 or 8-10), not only is there a 10-30 fold difference in retention time that can be exploited in method development but also the method can be made more robust which is a desirable outcome with validation in minutes [12,13]. Various steps for HPLC method development are given below.

Steps for HPLC method development

1. Information on sample
- ↓
2. Defining separation goals
- ↓
3. Special procedure requirement, sample pretreatment, if any
- ↓
4. Detector selection and setting
- ↓
5. Separation conditions optimization
- ↓
6. Checking for problems or special procedure requirements
- ↓
7. Recovery of purified material
- ↓
8. Quantitative calibration/ Qualitative method
- ↓
9. Method validation for release to laboratories

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

INSTRUMENTS USED

HPLC from WATERS, software: Empower 2, Alliance 2695 separation module. 996 PDA detector.

CHEMICALS USED:

Dicyclomine and Diclofenac K from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK) and Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck

METHOD VALIDATION

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Dicyclomine and Diclofenac K working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.3 ml of Dicyclomine and 0.6ml of Diclofenac K from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

(Optimized chromatogram) Standard:

Column	: Phenomenex Gemini C18 (4.6×250mm) 5μ
Column temperature	: 40°C
Wavelength	: 230nm
Mobile phase ratio	: Methanol: TEA Buffer (65:35 v/v)
Flow rate	: 1ml/min
Injection volume	: 10μl
Run time	: 7 minutes

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

PREPARATION OF BUFFER AND MOBILE PHASE:

Preparation of Triethylamine buffer (pH-4.0):

Take 6.0ml of Triethylamine in to 750ml of HPLC water in a 1000ml volumetric flask and mix well. Make up the volume up to mark with water and adjust the pH to 4.0 by using Orthophosphoric acid, filter and sonicate.

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 350 ml (35%) of TEA buffer and 650 ml of HPLC Methanol (65%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

Figure7.5: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table7.5: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Dicyclomine	3.202	2391746	39726	1.2	9028	
2	Diclofenac K	5.463	194627	8497	1.1	7398	7.4

Observation:

This trial shows improper separation sample peaks, baseline and show very less plate count in the chromatogram. So it's required more trials to obtain good peaks.

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Column : Phenomenex Gemini C18 (4.6×250mm) 5μ
 Column temperature : 40°C
 Wavelength : 230nm
 Mobile phase ratio : Methanol: TEA Buffer (65:35 v/v)
 Flow rate : 1ml/min
 Injection volume : 10μl
 Run time : 7 minutes

Figure7.6: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

Table7.6: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)

S. No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Dicyclomine	3.213	2381649	391846	1.2	9472	
2	Diclofenac K	5.478	191057	8104	1.1	8936	7.5

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY**Table7.7: Results of system suitability for Dicyclomine**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine	3.200	2391746	394171	8952	1.2
2	Dicyclomine	3.248	2391647	381946	9561	1.2
3	Dicyclomine	3.299	2381647	391746	6572	1.2
4	Dicyclomine	3.297	2385631	386562	6452	1.2
5	Dicyclomine	3.297	2385635	389164	7452	1.2
Mean			2387261			
Std. Dev.			4363.771			
% RSD			0.182794			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table7.8: Results of system suitability for Diclofenac K

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Diclofenac K	5.413	198362	7917	5272	1.1
2	Diclofenac K	5.484	197486	7486	6291	1.1
3	Diclofenac K	5.405	198354	7859	6184	1.1
4	Diclofenac K	5.405	197352	7926	7145	1.1
5	Diclofenac K	5.409	198453	7946	6946	1.1
Mean			198001.4			
Std. Dev.			535.1774			
% RSD			0.27029			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

ASSAY**Table7.9: Peak results for assay standard****Dicyclomine**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Dicyclomine	3.211	2397162	397161	1.2	9472
2	Dicyclomine	3.222	2394721	389173	1.2	9745
3	Dicyclomine	3.254	2389461	391723	1.2	8917

Diclofenac K

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Diclofenac K	5.414	198462	7811	1.1	8492	7.49
2	Diclofenac K	5.453	198472	8193	1.1	8916	7.52
3	Diclofenac K	5.424	198735	7972	1.1	9372	7.44

Table 7.10: Peak results for Assay sample**Dicyclomine**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Dicyclomine	3.297	2391741	381612	1.2	9472
2	Dicyclomine	3.294	2389166	391746	1.2	8927
3	Dicyclomine	3.295	2361731	381634	1.2	9017

Diclofenac K

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Diclofenac K	5.435	198641	8174	1.1	9284	7.18
2	Diclofenac K	5.417	196547	8942	1.1	8974	7.44
3	Diclofenac K	5.434	194027	7294	1.1	9017	7.38

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of **Dicyclomine** in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be **99.2%**.

The % purity of **Diclofenac K** in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be **99.5%**.

CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY:**DICYCLOMINE**

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
00	00
75	859889
150	1583641
225	2395378
300	3185089
375	3943725

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 29909. These values meet the validation criteria.

Diclofenac K

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Average Peak Area
00	00
15	61953
30	130213
45	198697
60	267002
75	321658

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 454.81. These values meet the validation criteria.

PRECISION:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

REPEATABILITY

Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table7.11: Results of repeatability for Dicyclomine

S.No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine	3.213	2397164	381741	8155	1.2
2	Dicyclomine	3.253	2391741	371742	9174	1.2
3	Dicyclomine	3.297	2371846	391746	7154	1.2
4	Dicyclomine	3.215	2361748	391847	9917	1.2
5	Dicyclomine	3.254	2371649	384622	9247	1.2
Mean			2378830			
Std.dev			14958			
%RSD			0.628797			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table7.12: Results of repeatability for Diclofenac K:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Diclofenac K	5.441	198464	7291	6274	1.1
2	Diclofenac K	5.442	193643	7219	6592	1.1
3	Diclofenac K	5.409	196462	7194	6028	1.1
4	Diclofenac K	5.520	194644	8174	6927	1.1
5	Diclofenac K	5.424	198464	8653	5920	1.1
Mean			196335.4			
Std.de v			2190.191			
%RSD			1.115536			

Intermediate precision:**Table7.13: Results of Intermediate precision for Dicyclomine**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine	3.211	2389572	395275	9375	1.2
2	Dicyclomine	3.211	2391847	392175	9275	1.2
3	Dicyclomine	3.210	2319472	312947	8265	1.2
4	Dicyclomine	3.212	2306842	310585	6254	1.2
5	Dicyclomine	3.211	2375972	310694	9028	1.2
6	Dicyclomine	3.297	2396746	358373	8928	1.2
Mean			2363409			
Std. Dev.			39730.83			
% RSD			1.681082			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table7.14: Results of Intermediate precision for Diclofenac K

S. No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Diclofenac K	5.411	197284	7194	8264	1.2
2	Diclofenac K	5.410	197849	7294	9174	1.2
3	Diclofenac K	5.420	196572	7147	9164	1.2
4	Diclofenac K	5.423	195028	7927	9733	1.2
5	Diclofenac K	5.419	199474	8238	9194	1.2
6	Diclofenac K	5.409	197482	7638	8973	1.2
Mean			197281.5			
Std. Dev.			1466.354			
% RSD			0.74328			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table7.15: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Dicyclomine

S. No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Dicyclomine	3.211	2389562	391741	9264	1.2
2	Dicyclomine	3.233	2381654	391047	9746	1.2
3	Dicyclomine	3.244	2381946	391748	9816	1.2
4	Dicyclomine	3.297	2391741	391746	9917	1.2
5	Dicyclomine	3.297	2386452	381641	9742	1.2
6	Dicyclomine	3.202	2374763	381645	9017	1.2
Mean			2384353			
Std. Dev.			6183.339			
% RSD			0.25933			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table7.16: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Diclofenac K

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Diclofenac K	5.411	197486	7582	6272	1.1
2	Diclofenac K	5.410	197486	7184	6174	1.1
3	Diclofenac K	5.420	196746	7456	5184	1.1
4	Diclofenac K	5.405	195862	7814	6194	1.1
5	Diclofenac K	5.409	196582	7194	6292	1.1
6	Diclofenac K	5.463	198463	7745	6191	1.1
Mean			197104.2			
Std. Dev.			903.542			
% RSD			0.458408			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

ACCURACY:**The accuracy results for Dicyclomine**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1217218	112.5	112.4	99.6	99.3
100%	2397141	225	225	100	
150%	3514547	337.5	332.5	98.5	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).
The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

The accuracy results for Diclofenac K

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	98598.67	22.5	22.4	99.9	99.6
100%	198359.7	45	45	100	
150%	291512.3	67.5	66.8	99	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).
The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Table7.20: Results for Robustness**Dicyclomine**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	2391746	3.202	9028	1.2
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	2371831	3.639	7381	1.2
More Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	2218319	2.859	9311	1.1
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	2294821	3.460	7462	1.2
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	2394811	3.022	6817	1.1

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Table7.21: Results for Robustness**Diclofenac K**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	194627	5.463	7398	1.1
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	183738	6.250	6883	1.1
More Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	198373	4.863	9917	1.2
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	178471	6.196	8372	1.1
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	189462	5.010	7716	1.2

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

CONCLUSION:

A new, accurate, and reliable reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Dicyclomine and Diclofenac Potassium in pharmaceutical formulations. The method employed a Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC system with a PDA Detector (996 model). Separation was achieved using a Phenomenex Gemini C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm) maintained at 40°C.

The optimized mobile phase consisted of Methanol and TEA buffer (65:35 v/v), delivered at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Detection was performed at 230 nm, and the injection volume was 10 μL, with a total run time of 7 minutes. The method demonstrated clear resolution of both analytes with good peak symmetry and reproducibility. The developed method was validated according to ICH guidelines, assessing parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), and robustness. The results confirmed that the method is suitable for routine quality control and simultaneous estimation of these drugs in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

The validated RP-HPLC method offers a simple, rapid, precise, and cost-effective approach for the simultaneous determination of Dicyclomine and Diclofenac Potassium. The optimized chromatographic conditions ensure effective resolution and sensitivity, meeting regulatory standards. Due to its reliability and reproducibility, the method is well-suited for routine analytical applications in pharmaceutical quality control laboratories.

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